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Research Article

A Study of Package Insert Analysis of Available Drugs in Local Market

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ABSTRACT

Context: The primary source of drug information is a Package Insert (PI) which is accurate and reliable. In India, the package insert is governed by the 'Drugs and Cosmetics Act (1940) and Rules (1945). The section 1 of Schedule Y of the rules lists the headings according to which information should be provided in the PIs. Aim: This study was undertaken to assess the completeness of information provided in PIs available in local pharmacies. Settings and Design: A prospective observational study was conducted from September 2023 to November 2023. Total 100 package inserts were taken in this study and they were collected from pharmacies located in various parts of Rajkot city. Methods and Material: 100 package inserts were analyzed based on 16 criteria mentioned in the Indian Drugs and Cosmetics Act (1940) and Rules (1945), under section 1 of schedule Y. Results: Only 5 PIs had all 16 criteria. 31% of PIs lacked information about Incompatibility, List of excipients, Instruction for Handling and about containers. 65% of PIs lacked same as above mentioned and additionally about overdosing, effects on ability to drive and use in pregnancy and lactation. Remaining 4% PIs contained information only about Posology and drug administration, contraindications, special warnings and D-D interactions. Conclusions: The information provided by PIs in India is inadequate, only 5 among 100 complied to the regulation, and they may not serve as a reliable source of information. It is, therefore recommended for strict compliance of PIs with criteria mentioned in Indian Drugs and Cosmetics Act (1940) and Rules (1945), under section 1 of schedule Y. Increased awareness, regular audits, and national-level policy reinforcement are essential steps to make PIs a more effective tool in rational drug use.

INTRODUCTION

To ensure the safe and effective use of marketed products, drug information must be both accurate

and dependable. The Package Insert (PI) serves as the primary and trustworthy source of this information.¹ It is written in a simple language that is not promotional or misleading.¹ It is evidence-

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based and is updated time to time with updated pre-clinical and clinical data.¹ Package insert, primarily directed at the prescribers, but is also provide information for the safe and effective use of the respective drug to patients and prescribers.² It is also known as Prescription drug label or Prescribing information.² In India, the package insert is governed by the 'Drugs and Cosmetics Act (1940) and Rules (1945), as amended in Drugs and Cosmetics (IIND AMENDMENT) Rules, in 20th January 2005 [Draft no- G.S.R35(E)].³ Section 1 of Schedule Y of the regulations outlines the headings under which information must be presented in the Package Inserts (PIs).³ Globally, regulatory bodies like the US FDA and the European Medicines Agency (EMA) maintain stringent requirements for PI contents. The FDA mandates comprehensive documentation under CFR Title 21, while EMA ensures harmonized, multilingual PIs across member states.⁴ These frameworks ensure patient safety, informed prescribing, and prevent medication errors. Previous studies have shown that, despite existing regulations, package inserts in India often lack sufficient information. Because PIs help to prevent mistakes when doctors prescribe, pharmacists dispense, and patients take medications. This could be one reason why medication errors happen less often.⁴ Despite existing Indian regulations, several studies report deficiencies in PI completeness. PIs help reduce prescription, dispensing, and administration errors. In India, with a doctor-patient ratio of 1:1700, the availability of reliable written information like PIs becomes even more crucial.⁷ This study aims to evaluate whether locally available PIs comply with Indian legal standards and how they fare in terms of completeness.

METHODS

A prospective observational study was conducted from September 2023 to November 2023. Total 100 package inserts were taken in this study and they were collected from pharmacies located in various parts of Rajkot city. They were analyzed based on 16 criteria mentioned in the Indian Drugs and Cosmetics Act (1940) and Rules (1945), under section 1 of schedule Y, as amended in the 20th January, 2005. The study was done after obtaining approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee. The data was entered into excel sheet (version 2016). Data analysis was done by using the percentages. The package inserts must adhere to the specified headings outlined in Section '1' of Schedule Y, within the Drugs and Cosmetics Act (1940) and Rules (1945). These sections encompass essential information, including: [generic name; composition; dosage form/s; indications; dose and method of administration; use in special populations (such as pregnant women, lactating women, pediatric patients, geriatric patients etc.); contra-indications; warnings; precautions; drug interactions; undesirable effects; overdose, incompatibilities; shelf-life; packaging information; storage and handling instructions.] We divided these 16 criteria in 3 classes Class A (12-16), Class B (6-11) and Class C (0-5) according to total criteria presented. The classification helped identify trends in compliance and allowed sub-analysis based on drug category and company origin.

RESULTS

From 100 Package inserts, 87 PIs belonged to India based company and 13 PIs were from foreign based multinational company (Fig-1). Majority of drugs belongs to Anti-diabetics, Anti-bacterial and Anti-hypertensive. Only 5 Package inserts were containing 100% information as mentioned in Indian Drugs and Cosmetics Act (1940) and Rules (1945), under section 1 of schedule Y. 31 PIs

belonged to Class ‘A’, 65 PIs belonged to Class ‘B’ and remaining 4 PIs belonged to Class ‘C’ (Fig-2). 31% of PIs (Class-A) lacked information about Incompatibility, List of excipients, Instruction for Handling and about containers. 65% of PIs(Class-B) lacked same as above mentioned and additionally about overdosing, effects on ability to drive and use in pregnancy and lactation. Remaining 4% PIs(Class-C) contained information only about Posology and drug administration, contraindications, special

warnings and D-D interactions. When comparing Indian and foreign PIs, foreign PIs showed slightly better compliance (especially regarding overdose management and excipient listing), though none met all 16 points. Drug category-wise, anti-hypertensive had higher compliance than anti-bacterial. The Completeness of information in the package inserts with respect to headings under Section ‘1’ of Schedule Y, Drugs and Cosmetics Act (1940) and Rules (1945) are showing in Table-1.

Fig- 1- Origin of Companies of PIs

Fig- 2- Class of PIs

Table-1: Completeness of information in the package inserts with respect to headings under Section ‘1’ of Schedule Y, Drugs and Cosmetics Act (1940) and Rules (1945).

No.	Criteria	Present in PIs
1	Posology and method of administration	100%
2	Contraindications	99%
3	Special warnings and precautions for use	96%
4	Interaction with other medicaments and other forms of interaction	95%
5	Pregnancy and lactation, if contra-indicated	91%
6	Effects of ability to drive and use machines, if contra-indicated	46%
7	Undesirable effects/side effects	99%
8	Antidote for overdosing	81%
9	List of Excipients	55%
10	Incompatibilities	31%
11	Shelf life in the medical product as packaged for sale	34%
12	Shelf life after dilution or reconstitution according to direction	-

13	Shelf life after first opening the container	-
14	Special precautions for storage	92%
15	Nature and specification of the containers	63%
16	Instructions for use/handling	42%

DISCUSSION

To achieve safe and effective use of drugs, the prescribers have to be up-to-date with appropriate and accurate information regarding the medication.⁵ In India, the ratio of doctors to patients stands at 1:1700, whereas the recommended ratio is 1:1000.⁷ This disparity presents challenges for doctors to provide comprehensive information about medications, and for patients to retain such details.⁶ So, a package insert acts as reliable source of information, for both prescribers and patients. Efforts to enhance the content of package inserts are not only underway in India but also in other countries such as Europe, the USA, Australia, and Saudi Arabia.⁶ This study has noted a general enhancement in the completeness of the package inserts concerning therapeutic information. The percentage of inserts giving detailed information regarding the Posology and drug administered, contraindications and undesirable effects is respectively 100%, 99%, and 99% in comparison to 98%, 96%, and 97% respectively in the study conducted by Chhaya MU et al⁵ and 90%, 96% and 98% respectively in the Yuwnate AH et al⁶. The pharmaceutical information also seems to be improved like information about Excipients (55%), Incompatibilities (31%), Shelf life (34%) in comparison to 12%, 19% and 16% respectively in the study conducted by Chhaya MU et al⁵ and Although the quality of package inserts has improved, there is scope for further improvements in therapeutic as well as pharmaceutical information. Many a times, package inserts for the same drug from different companies may have

differing information. A post publishing surveillance to avoid such confusion would be beneficial. Unfortunately, we noted that many pharmacies discard package inserts due to a lack of understanding of their significance, deeming them unnecessary bulk in packaging. Additionally, the widespread practice of dispensing drugs without prescriptions exacerbates this issue, resulting in patients missing out on valuable package inserts that could have provided essential information. The common practice of dispensing drugs without prescriptions means many patients never receive a PI at all. This undermines the utility of even well-crafted PIs. Although regulatory frameworks are well established under the Drugs and Cosmetics Act and Schedule Y, there remains a gap between regulation and enforcement. While manufacturers are legally obliged to update and standardize PIs, there is little oversight or penalty for non-compliance. Unlike the United States where FDA labeling reviews are mandatory for approval, in India, post-marketing audits are sporadic and often overlooked. Moreover, the lack of centralized PI repositories or publicly accessible databases hinders accountability. Bridging this gap would require coordinated efforts from the CDSCO, IPC, and medical colleges to initiate auditing, training, and educational outreach to ensure every stakeholder—from pharmaceutical companies to end-users—understands the importance of PI compliance.

❖ To Enhance the Value of PIs:

- ✓ Regulatory audits by CDSCO should be conducted periodically.
- ✓ PIs should be made available in regional languages for patient accessibility.
- ✓ Digital PIs via QR codes could ensure access to the latest version.
- ✓ Pharmacists should be trained to provide and explain PIs during dispensing.
- ✓ Pharmaceutical companies must align local PIs with international quality benchmarks.

Limitations

The study focused exclusively on package inserts for orally administered and locally available drugs. If we included package inserts of topical and injectable drugs, it would give more detailed results.

Future-Scope

Future studies should include PIs of non-oral dosage forms like injectable, topical, and ophthalmic preparations to provide a more comprehensive overview. Further, comparative studies between different regions in India or across countries could offer insights into regulatory and compliance differences. Qualitative assessments of readability, language simplicity, and pictorial usage in PIs could also be valuable. Finally, evaluating the impact of updated PIs on patient outcomes and medication adherence would contribute significantly to public health policy.

CONCLUSION

In India, the information provided by Package Inserts (PIs) is often insufficient, with only 5 out of 100 meeting regulatory standards, making them potentially unreliable sources of information. It is, therefore recommended for strict compliance of PIs with criteria mentioned in Indian Drugs and Cosmetics Act (1940) and Rules (1945), under section 1 of schedule Y.

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